

Cultural Sensitivity in Travelling: An Educational Approach with the CultSense Project

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10051577

Introduction

For centuries, people have travelled to learn about other cultures and customs. Since the popularisation of the Grand Tour, travel in its leisurely form has introduced an educational angle to mobility. Specific types of tourism have developed to respond to the willingness and eagerness to learn in the different ways, such as cultural tourism, heritage tourism, war tourism, or creative tourism, which have a strong learning component.

Yet, although the educational value of tourism has been well studied, the need to sensitize tourists themselves (and visitors in general) about the impact of their travels and presence in cultures different than their own has remained under the radar. Propelled by the development of globalised and democratised travelling, the early 2000s saw the rise in different documents, guidelines and campaigns emphasizing the necessity of somehow “educating the tourists” (Marques 2021). Two examples are the Cape Town Declaration on Responsible Tourism (2002) and the guidelines for the responsible and ethically sustainable use of Sámi cultural features (2018 qtd by Kugapi et al., 2020). The need for ethical forms of tourism and the role of (tourism) education has also been a focus of attention (Tribe, 2002), education being posited as a means to tackle the negative impacts of tourism (e.g. pressures on carrying capacity, commoditization of culture, gentrification).

Between the need to “educate the tourist” and the wish of a tourism experience with a learning component, two complementary movements can be pinpointed – one from the policy side, another one from the demand. While policy focuses on guidelines to support what is considered government priority (e.g. China’s Guidebook for Civilised Tourism, 2013), demand concentrates on looking for more meaningful and local experiences (e.g. creative tourism practices). Tourism agents and local cultural organizations, however, seem yet to be giving infant steps on engaging actively in sensitizing visitors. Nevertheless, some forms of circular tourism, regenerative tourism and creative

To cite: Marques, L. & Driessen, S. (2023) Cultural Sensitivity in Travelling: An Educational Approach with the CultSense Project / Culturele sensitiviteit bij reizen: Een educatieve aanpak dankzij het CultSense-project. *Vrijetijdstudies*, VTS 2023-1. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10051577

tourism have embedded elements of this sensitization process. Therefore, in terms of supply, initiatives are developing which aim at – or at least include – forms of sensitizing visitors. An examples can be seen in the Arctic, with the valorisation of indigenous Sámi lifestyle, customs, crafts and culture, within the project ARCTISEN (<https://sensitivetourism.interreg-npa.eu/>). Another example is the valorisation of local cultures in Higher Education (HE) within the CultSense project (www.cultsense.com). Such initiatives aim at bridging a gap between locals and visitors (including domestic and international tourists), paving the way to further understanding and dialogue across cultures.

1. On Cultural Sensitivity

If intercultural communication has been largely studied in different contexts, cultural sensitivity however is more scarcely scrutinized in leisure, and less so in tourism. This can be partly explained by the fact that cultural sensitivity is a complex and fuzzy concept prone to a range of multiple – if not contradictory – interpretations (Viken, Höckert & Grimwood 2021; Engberg et al., 2022). The conceptual reflection by Viken, Höckert & Grimwood (2021), developed within the ARCTISEN project, outlines cultural sensitivity in tourism as “a disposition that can be enhanced and mobilized through reflection on one’s own pre-assumptions, cultural norms and values” (Viken, Höckert, and Grimwood 2021, p.3). Building on this rationale, Marques & Engberg (2022: 7-8) include other elements, considering that “cultural sensitivity is a disposition, an awareness, a mindset, and a competence which can become a fertile ground for a more positive (tourism) experience”. While authors in the first study shift away from the idea of competence, Marques & Engberg (2022) embrace it, positioning cultural sensitivity in the educational turn in tourism. Furthermore, postulating it as a competence, allows us to expand on a previous body of knowledge related to intercultural communication and intercultural competences, establishing important dimensions of cultural sensitivity. Without intercultural proficiency, respect and openness, we argue, one cannot claim to be culturally-sensitive.

Challenges in measuring, developing and nurturing a multi-dimensional competence such as cultural sensitivity abound. Reflection and perception of the Self and the Other need to be included, as it becomes evident from the study by Chen and Starosta (2000). These authors have developed an Intercultural Sensitivity Scale, in which intercultural sensitivity is considered an affective dimension. Fan et al. (2021) later researched intercultural competences in the framework of cultural tourism, as cultural tourists are motivated by acquiring knowledge about other cultures, and learning is a strong component of their experience. Factors of intercultural responsibility, understanding, appreciation,

and action were pinpointed, which contribute to an enhanced tourism experience, specifically when active participation occurs.

These factors are partly confirmed in the five areas of cultural sensitivity identified in the Sámi tourism in Finland (Saari et al. 2020): respect, cultural sustainability, cultural carrying capacity, cultural representations, and cultural identity. Healing, reconciliation and recognition are also examined in the Sámi context. Along the same line, Hurst et al. (2021) establish seven themes of cultural sensitivity in indigenous tourism: respect, trust, ethics, cultural identity, mutual understanding and cultural exchange, self-determination, governance, and capacity building, and unique healing, wellness, and spiritual needs. Understanding culturally-sensitive dimensions of tourism relates both in their relation to local cultures, “as culturally sensitive activities and interactions (...) are interpreted as culturally contingent, place-based and context-specific” (Hurst et al., 2021: 501), and to overall fundamental dimensions which “transcend the context-specific examples” (Hurst et al., 2021: 501).

2. The CultSense Project

Focussing specifically on Higher Education, the project CultSense – Sensitizing Young Travellers to Local Cultures, emphasizes three aspects: i) youth travel; ii) interchange in roles of visitors and locals; iii) sensitization of future professionals in the fields of Tourism, Leisure and Culture (TLC). In its core, CultSense fosters understanding, respect, and a sense of responsibility towards local cultures and its various expressions, from tangible to intangible heritage, from traditional to innovative customs, rituals and lifestyles.

As a project, CultSense first aim is to develop tools for sensitizing young travellers to understand and respect better the local norms, values, beliefs and cultures of the places they visit. The underlying assumption is that the recognition and awareness of visited cultures goes hand-in-hand with a deeper understanding of one’s own culture. Appreciating your own culture would, in principle, contribute to understanding its relation to other cultures, In this sense, the project pursues markedly the educational turn in tourism, fostering forms of sensitized tourism. The tourism experience is then multi-dimensional, and it should be tackled from its different perspectives of (formal and informal) education, encouraging (intercultural) awareness from hosts, visitors and service providers, and an appreciation that every human being can have a role as host and/or visitor. CultSense stimulates co-creation at two levels: 1) among teachers, through training, reflection, co-production of tools, collaborations in guest lectures and other projects; 2) between teachers, students and other staff (e.g. international officers), through trainings, co-production of materials,

such as videos or case studies, focus groups, classes. This co-creative environment allows space for a bottom-up approach in terms of awareness, working from within, with young people. The role of educators and academia in the process of training youth is fundamental, as the younger generations will become the future professionals in many different areas, directly or indirectly related to tourism, culture and leisure. They are also the tourists of the present and of the future. These young professionals can thus have an impact on the services offered, which can be framed as more meaningful and locally connected experiences. In this sense, the project has also provided a space for local actors to voice their experiences, in particular regarding global intercultural awareness for (young) travellers.

3. Dimensions of Cultural Sensitivity and Perceived Travel Benefits

Within this framework, drawing on previous studies, CultSense understands cultural sensitivity as a multidimensional and complex competence which can be grasped through four dimensions at the crossing of the axes Passive-Active and Self-Other: Self-Observation, Self-Development, Socio-Cultural Exchange, and Active Stewardship (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Culturally-sensitive tourism experience dimensions

As with the four realms of an experience by Pine and Gilmore (1998), the optimal culturally-sensitive tourism experience would be a combination of the four dimensions. Underlying any of the dimensions are values such as respect, trust, cultural identity, and mutual understanding and cultural exchange.

Within CultSense, a large mixed-methods research has been carried out, which includes a survey among students from eight HEI in five European countries: the Netherlands, Finland, Romania, Spain and Portugal. With a total of 1611 valid responses collected longitudinally during three academic years, between September 2020 and November 2022. Even though the data was collected during the COVID-19 pandemic, questions referred specifically to the last international journey. Part of the research aims is to understand cultural sensitivity in the tourism experience and how it relates to perceived travel benefits. The latter were scored in a 5 point Likert scale (see Figure 2 for the means).

Analysis shows that all items were perceived positively, although learning a language is the lowest ($\mu=2.64$). This could be explained by the amount of time necessary for actively learning a language. The feeling of contributing to places is also positive, albeit low ($\mu=3.26$). Appreciation for the local culture ($\mu=3.97$) and a sense of broadening horizons ($\mu=4.07$) score relatively high, with appetite for even more travel scoring the highest ($\mu=4.52$). These findings seemingly corroborate that youth travel has affinities with local culture (WYSE, 2018), suggesting that the relationship and experience could be enhanced, for example, with further cultural sensitivity and intercultural awareness.

Figure 2. Perceived Travel Benefits

Final Remarks

Within CultSense, the role of education and active learning in the tourism experience and its perceived travel benefits has been highlighted through the co-creation of a range of digital-friendly tools. A Framework for Co-creative Cultural Awareness (FCCA) (Marques et al, 2021 in Marques, Aulet & Oliveira, 2023: 17) was created which aims at activating students. Besides, a methodological approach which forms the core of the academic soundness of the project (Marques, Aulet and Oliveira, 2023), videos, a case studies eBook, five learning modules and a pedagogical toolkit are available in open access. Although firstly thought to TLC Higher Education programmes, the objectives and tools of this project could potentially be used in any study programme and level as part of transferable skills. Further educational activities, research and industry collaborations are needed to better tackle cultural sensitivity in tourism and leisure contexts.

In the face of global societal challenges, and increased pressures related to mobilities, visible ever more strongly in the post-pandemic recovery, the overall purpose of CultSense consists of further contributing to socio-cultural sustainability. It is another piece in the array of extant initiatives aiming at smoothening tensions and conflicts between locals and visitors through the valorisation and development of cultural sensitivity. The younger generations are the active stewards of past and living heritage that uphold the future of our cultural identities.

Acknowledgements

The authors are grateful for all the discussions with the CultSense team.

Funding

This work was supported by the Project “CULTSENSE – Sensitizing young tourists for local cultures”, number 2020-1-NL01-KA203-064791, funded by Erasmus+ programme.

Disclosure statement

The European Commission's support for the production of this publication does not constitute an endorsement of the contents, which reflect the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein. A version of this text was published in Dutch, in *Vrijetijdstudies* 2023-1.

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